

Direct Marketing Channels and Strategy for Organic Products

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Abstract

Farmers approach direct marketing in a variety of ways using single or multiple channels. The goal generally is to develop a strategy to sell the entire product they produce. This can be through one marketing channel or several. Farms may also add additional direct market channels as the business grows. For instance, many farmers begin with selling through a farmers' market or a roadside stand. As the business grows, they can add other direct channels such as a CSA, grocery or restaurant sales. Direct sales channels for specific crops or a segment of a crop may be combined with wholesale channels. The options are nearly endless.

Most successful small to medium-sized organic farmers will rely on a diverse number of marketing channels rather than rely on a single buyer. Organic farmers use farmers markets, on-farm sales, restaurant accounts in preference to wholesale as marketing outlets. Retail and wholesale distributors will often be used as outlet channels when available. Large farms tend to rely on advance contracts with processors and high volume retail sales. The largest farms are vertically integrated as packer-shippers, paralleling the conventional channels for distribution. Packer-shipper operations will contract with producers, particularly in cases where the producers can fill different market windows. With a growing number of organic food processors entering the market, an increased volume of purchases goes through contracted channels. Spot market sales and terminal markets have been the least profitable outlets for organic farmers. With rare exceptions, these markets will not pay a premium for the organic product.

Keywords: Organic food products, distribution, consumers, intermediaries, retails, wholesale distributors. Peasant markets, Community Supported Agriculture—CSA, Farmers' Markets

Choosing the Distribution Channels

It is indicated for the farmer to use the distribution channels in which to interact with several customers to have higher profits. It is easier for farmers to work with fewer customers but in this case the chances are that profits to be lower, distribution channels have been classified into three categories: direct (sales direct from the farm), short (including farmers markets, organic stores specialized, home delivery, restaurants) and traditional (deliveries to supermarkets, sales to wholesalers or delivery through cooperatives). The level of education and professional training adversely affect farmers' choice

for traditional channels and in a positive way the choice for modern channels (direct or short). In large farms it is noted the preference towards traditional channels, unlike small farms where production volume allows the option for modern distribution channels. The location of the farm is important because farmers from the mountains or hilly areas prefer to sell through direct or short distribution channels because their production costs are higher and require higher sales prices to survive on the market. Of type produced on the farm also influences inclination to a method of marketing. Thus, those who produce grain or other crops on large areas of fields that can be stored and processed harder prefer traditional distribution channels. Farmers who produce products that can be sold in smaller quantities throughout the year prefer rather short and direct distribution channels identified the types of farms whose products are distributed through a single channel of distribution. These are family farms, farms with a single owner, farms that made the transition from conventional agriculture to the organic, farms run by less experienced farmers and farms managing a large number of hectares. There are organic farms where they observe a preference for the use of multiple types of distribution channels. These farms are run by experienced farmers and have a greater number of employees.

There are many approaches to direct farm marketing. Some have been around for decades others are have been developed more recently. The most common types of direct marketing are:

Community Supported Agriculture—CSA

Community supported agriculture is a relatively recent and innovative concept that is intended to create a relationship between farmers and consumers wherein risks and bounties are shared. CSA customers buy shares for a season by paying a fee in advance. In return, they receive a regular (in most cases weekly) selection of food. Having cash in advance of the growing season and a regular customer following provide financial security for farmers. The regular supply of food grown on the farm provides nutritional security and a sense of community for customers. On some farms, get-togethers with customers or workdays are part of the agreement. In its purest form, customers share in the risk of low production and crop failures, as well as any abundance, by receiving less or more food. This aspect has seen a variety of adaptations on CSA farms.

Farmers' Markets

A farmers' market is a place where some growers assemble on a particular day to sell farm products directly to consumers. The sites are often parking lots; streets closed during the market, parks, etc. Farmers at these markets sell their products from "stands" that may consist of the back of a farm truck or a simple tabletop to elaborate and attractive covered displays.

Farmers generally receive retail prices or higher for their products. Start-up costs for becoming involved in a farmers' market can be very inexpensive—just a stall fee in some instances. Because of the low start-up investment, farmers' markets can provide a low-risk setting for new farmers or an opportunity to try out new products. Many farmers participate in more than one market to increase their sales.

Farmers' markets also provide the opportunity to build a customer base. Some farms advertise other outlets for buying their products (other farm direct marketing methods, or retail stores for instance).

Box Schemes

Marketing of "box schemes" type consists OF delivering at the consumer home by a company that is supplied by one or more farmers at a fixed price. In some cases, farmers assume the role of coordination in 22 of these systems. This type of marketing has become very important in developed

markets where demand exceeds the capacity of farmers to produce and deliver. Regarding the motivations of consumers who prefer this mode of acquisition, it was found that altruistic motivations are prevailing in England, while in France the quality egocentric motivations prevail. The most important barriers that prevent local consumption are the desire to eat fruit and vegetables in extra-season in England, while in France stood out the price and limited range of products. Denmark and UK systems there are types of 'box schemes' where some products are imported because of the need to satisfy the demand increasingly diverse of fruits and vegetables. There are companies that deliver fruits and vegetables weekly to 25000 customers, while other companies are delivering to some dozens of customers. It is necessary for producers to associate so that they could be available to deliver more product lines to maintain the local nature of consumption. Consumer's requirements that prefer this system are becoming more refined and in these systems involve increasingly larger companies who are treating the issue of competitiveness in a very efficient way but who can remove the system from the original purpose, to help local consumption. There are people involved in organic farming since the early stages and are unhappy about the character more and more mercantile activity of this field and begin to understand that their actions in this field must be oriented to the customer, to market. Most of those seeking "box schemes" are aged 45 years or older have average or above average income. Despite the local contribution to consumption growth and incipient development of organic farming systems 'box schemes' are still at the stage of niche, and so that organic farming to impose is needed the supermarkets.

Peasant Markets

Peasant markets for of have become an option increasingly important in recent years, and motivation of buyers from these markets varies. It is interesting to find that not only the sales increased but also the number of peasant markets. There is a segment of buyers who go to markets to be seen that they have financial possibilities to buy off. The main benefits sought by buyers in peasant markets are: - Fresh, healthy and seasonal; - Stimulate the local economy; - Develop confidence, the good atmosphere that stimulates communication. As main disadvantages are: - The long duration of time needed to achieve the purchase; - Possibility to buy OF only in season. It was found that the tendency to buy off is greater among people who use to attend the peasant markets where they find agricultural products obtained in the conventional manner (OECD Journal). It is much easier to communicate to the customer the value and importance OF when marketing is done by peasant markets, unlike the situation in which trading is done by more sophisticated methods, such as supermarkets. Generally, farmers who sell their OF in peasant markets are in a less stable financially situation, but in the event of exceptional situations such as turbulence on OF market, they are better positioned than farmers who rely on intermediaries. 23 Peasant markets are one of the first ways used for distribution in early-stage markets. People who attend the peasant markets are educated and have a higher income than in average and are likely to have ecological lifestyles show that in peasant markets consumers have the opportunity to learn concepts on how to use and to conserve food, taste, availability, and quality of various products. Also, farmers have the opportunity to learn about consumer preferences, their tastes and their abilities to use food products provided. This learning is very useful because it can effectively guide decisions and behavior of those involved in food production and consumption. Trust, the loyalty which is built constitutes premises of sustainable development. Farm shops To maximize the effectiveness of these shops, it should be considering the following aspects: creating a business vision, attracting and retaining of the customers, appropriate product range and promoting. In the following years, most of these stores will also have an online component and will have to focus on finding more efficient ways of communicating the value of these products. This way of trading has the following advantages: direct

contact between customers and producers PAE niche can be developed the relaxing atmosphere in a rural location These stores must be located near cities or near highly traveled roads and need to be open evenings and in weekends. People in higher social classes have less time to go to the farm to buy from stores thereof. Communication should focus on the sanogenetic character and environmental of the products. Unlike the peasant markets, where consumers are going more to be seen, in the case of the farm stores, buyers go out of conviction, with the clear intention to buy and conspicuous component of the acquisition is less obvious.

U-Pick Farms

U-Pick or Pick-Your-Own farms grow crops specifically to be harvested by customers. In this manner, the task of picking the crop, one of the higher costs of growing fruits and vegetables, is passed on to customers. U-Pick farms have traditionally appealed to families who do home canning. There continues to be an interest by families in picking produce for fresh use and, in some instances, having their children experience where their food comes from. As with many direct marketing techniques, U-Pick operations can be blended with other marketing techniques such as roadside markets, farmers' markets, and so on.

Farm Stands

Farm stands or markets are structures of some type from which the farm's products are sold. They can range in sophistication from a stand with a coffee can for purchases by honor system to a building with refrigerated storage and several employees. They tend to be located on the farm, often on a well-traveled road with good access and parking. They can operate seasonally or all year and focus on one product or a full line of products. Roadside markets usually charge near retail prices. Given that farm stands or markets are structures, they are subject to local building codes and highway setback regulations.

Restaurants

Many farms are now marketing directly to restaurants providing the specific products and the high quality that chefs are demanding. Many restaurants cultivate relationships with farms even noting the farm name and its product on their menu. These restaurants serve a niche of customers who find high-quality food produced locally appealing. Supporting local farms is a philosophical goal for these restaurants.

Similar opportunities for direct farm sales are to institutions that serve food large or "captive" groups such as:

- Hospitals
- Retirement and nursing facilities
- More

Tip Sheets

Selling directly to restaurants, retailers and institutions can be a great way to expand your business and develop a reliable customer base. Created by Community Involved in Sustaining Agriculture (CISA), these tip sheets are designed to help farmers respond to the unique challenges in reaching out to and maintaining relationships with buyers.

Agritourism

Agritourism appeals to customers who have a desire to visit a farm and experience its activities. As Americans lose family ties with agriculture, many are interested in maintaining some sort

of contact with farming;, especially for their children. This is a theme with most types of direct marketing but is a key feature of Agritourism. There are a variety of approaches.

Online Marketing

The internet provides a convenient method to advertise the farm business, sell products, and communicate with customers. Most households have access to the internet in their homes. This is a potentially large market for specialty farm products.

Farms may advertise on the internet by developing their web sites or by participating in web-based farm directories. Farm homepages are an effective means of informing customers of products the farm grows, when they are available, and how to obtain them. Related blogs report on-farm or family activities. A farm may offer details on its CSA or identify which farmers' markets it sells at. These types of web pages allow customers to see the farm and the people who work there. This enhances the personal aspect of direct farm marketing that many people find appealing. There are also opportunities for sales via the internet. Value-added or even fresh food products may be shipped to customers throughout the country. The internet is a quick and easy method for communicating with established customers. The latest information on product availability, farm news, and other information may be distributed to customers through an email list

Conclusions

The choice over the distribution channel is very important. Farmers can choose the channels without 24 intermediaries (distribution type "box schemes," CSA system, peasant markets and farm shops) or may choose indirect channels (through supermarkets, specialized organic shops, restaurants, processors and various intermediaries). Each of these options carries certain advantages and disadvantages and the choice should be based on factors such as farm size, specific of production, the degree of market development and farm location. Regardless of the main distribution method selected by the farmer, for safety reasons their use is recommended at least two types of distribution channels in order not to depend on only one version where there is a risk of syncope. Also, especially for smaller farms is good to keep a close connection with the final customer, who must and can be sensitized towards supporting local agriculture and economy. Such a close relationship with the final user will allow farmers to easily overcome problems that may arise on the of the market due to fluctuations inherent in a market such sensitive as of.

Web Sources

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